

Knowledge and Attitude of Antibiotic use and Resistance among Doctors at a Tertiary Care Hospital: A Cross-Sectional Study**Vaishaliben Mavjibhai Solanki¹, Kamleshkumar G Rathod², Hitesh Assudani³, Krupali Kothari⁴, Jimishaben Rathwa⁵**^{1,5}Junior Resident, ²Associate Professor, ^{3,4}Professor^{1,3,4,5}Department of Microbiology, Gujarat Adani Institute of Medical Sciences, Bhuj, Gujarat²Department of Pediatrics, C.U. Shah Medical College & Hospital, Surendranagar, Gujarat

Received: 25-09-2024 / Revised: 23-10-2024 / Accepted: 25-11-2024

Corresponding Author: Dr. Kamleshkumar G Rathod

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Introduction: Antibiotic resistance is an emerging global health threat with significant implications in tertiary care settings, where doctors often use antibiotics to treat complex patients. This study aims to assess the knowledge and attitudes of doctors regarding antibiotic resistance in a tertiary hospital, with a focus on identifying knowledge gaps that could guide the development of effective antibiotic stewardship programs.

Methods: A cross-sectional survey was conducted at GAIMS Bhuj using a structured questionnaire. The study targeted intern doctors, resident doctors, and faculty members. The questionnaire was developed through a review of literature and expert consultation and piloted for clarity and reliability. Two months data were collected using Google Forms and response rate was 98.7%. Data were analyzed in Microsoft Excel and SPSS using chi-square tests for statistical significance.

Results: The study revealed that 96.67% of respondents were aware of AMR, but only 88% considered it a serious issue. Misconceptions regarding antibiotic prescription were common, including the belief that broad-spectrum antibiotics can be started for less severe infections, with 49.33% of the respondents agreeing to such practices. There was a weak positive correlation between educational qualification and AMR knowledge ($r = 0.21$), and education level has mild effects on attitudes toward AMR. Educational qualifications indicated high significance regarding associations with AMR awareness, with a p-value of 0.03.

Conclusion: Even though awareness among the health professionals is at the right level, knowledge misapplications and gaps do remain in this area of drug prescription, especially as relates to antibiotics. This article depicts a continuous need for education while antibiotic stewardship programs are established at all levels to fill knowledge gap with practice. There remains an important need to infuse knowledge into prescription procedures as an effective method in AMR management supported with guidelines from institutions to control dissemination and enhance outcomes.

Keywords: Antibiotic resistance, medical interns, physicians, Knowledge and attitudes, Tertiary care hospital, Antibiotic stewardship.

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

The unchecked rise in antibiotic resistance poses a serious and imminent threat to public health, ushering in the post-antibiotic era, when even minor infections may produce severe and life-threatening results [1]. Rapid and widespread resistant pathogens undermine all the currently available antibiotics leading to increased periods of disease, costlier health service delivery, and increased mortalities [2]. In light of this scale of the antibiotic resistance crisis, knowledge, attitude, and practice of doctors, especially those doctors, who are involved in clinical practice and prescribing or usage of antibiotics, has great importance [3]. Doctors in tertiary care hospitals mainly deal with complex cases in which high-

intensity usage of antibiotics is usually made. Thus, these are the key professionals that reduce the transmission of antimicrobial resistance. Their knowledge and attitudes towards resistance are critical to the development of effective antibiotic stewardship programs seeking to reduce resistance and promote optimum prescribing practices [4]. This study seeks to assess the Knowledge and Attitude of doctors regarding antibiotic use and resistance within a tertiary care hospital, with an aim at identifying areas of knowledge gaps and places where practice can be improved [5]. With the help of a cross-sectional design, the study delivers an extensive snap of current Knowledge and Attitude amongst doctors in a tertiary care

setting that offers an understanding of the areas in dire need of immediate adjustment and change in clinical practice against the alarming rise in the spread of antimicrobial resistance. Moreover, findings of the research would help form the basis for education policies and policy recommendations intended to develop antibiotic stewardship and prescribe antibiotics effectively in combating this growing menace of antibiotic resistance [6].

Methodology:

Study Design: This study was conducted as a cross-sectional survey using a structured questionnaire. The study aims to assess the knowledge and attitude regarding antibiotic resistance among doctors at a tertiary care hospital, GAIMS Bhuj.

Study population: All doctors of tertiary care hospital. Participants were selected purposively.

Inclusion Criteria: Intern doctors, resident doctors and faculties. excluding doctors not involved in patient care.

Sample Size: The sample size was calculated with a confidence level of 90%, an anticipated prevalence of 50% (chosen to maximize variability due to unknown prevalence), and a margin of error set at approximately 7%.

Data Collection Tool: A structured questionnaire was developed, consisting of four sections:

1. Demographics: Age, gender, Educational Qualification
2. Knowledge: Questions assessing the understanding of antimicrobial resistance, its causes and consequences.
3. Attitude: Questions exploring beliefs and perceptions about antibiotic resistance and its impact on patient care.

Questionnaire Development: Literature Review: The questionnaire was developed based on a thorough review of existing literature. Expert Review: The draft questionnaire was reviewed by a panel of experts in infectious diseases, pharmacology and clinical practice to ensure content validity. Pilot Testing: Questionnaire testing was conducted with 15 doctors who were consulted on the clarity, relevance, and response options. Based upon their feedback, items were rephrased for clarity and response options were expanded to boost the reliability and validity of the questionnaire.

Data Collection Procedure: the questionnaire was distributed electronically via **Google Forms**. An initial email invitation was sent to all eligible doctors, emphasizing that **all questions were compulsory** to ensure completeness of data. To

maximize the response rate, two reminder emails were sent at one-week intervals. The final response rate was 98.7%, with no missing data, as the online platform required responses to each question before submission. Data was collected over a period of 2 months from December 2023 to February 2024.

Informed Consent: Participants were informed about the purpose of the study, voluntary participation and their right to withdraw at any time.

Confidentiality: Responses were anonymous and data was stored securely to ensure confidentiality.

Data Analysis: There is no missing data as all the questions were compulsory to submit the responses. Data was entered and analysed using statistical software Microsoft excel 2019, Epi Info and SPSS, frequency and percentage were calculated and chi square test was applied for comparison. Ethical approval for this study was granted by Gujarat Adani Institute of Medical Sciences, Bhuj, Gujarat., with approval number GAIMS/IEC/APPROVAL/2023/2/3R.

Confidentiality was maintained by anonymizing participant data, assigning unique identifiers, and securely storing data on password-protected servers accessible only to authorized personnel. Informed consent was obtained from all participants, detailing their rights and the purpose of the study, with clear options to withdraw at any time. No conflicts of interest were reported.

Results

The results of the study revealed important insights into the demographics, knowledge, and attitudes regarding antibiotic resistance among participants. In terms of demographics, the age distribution showed that 54% of participants were between 21-25 years, 13.33% were 26-30 years, 15.33% were 31-35 years, 8% were 36-40 years, and 10% were over 40 years. The gender distribution indicated that 62.67% were male and 37.33% were female. Regarding educational qualifications, 4% of participants had a Doctorate, 47.33% were intern doctors, 41.33% had a postgraduate degree, and 7.33% had a postgraduate diploma.

Knowledge on Use of Antibiotics and Resistance: A large proportion (96.67%) were aware of AMR, but only 88% of them perceived it as a serious problem. Knowledge about the antibiotic action was not uniform; 62% stated that antibiotics were potent against bacterial infections, whereas 38% admitted to potency against both bacterial and viral infections. 64% of the respondents acknowledged that overuse of antimicrobial agents leads to reduced efficacy, adverse effects, increased costs and prolonged illness. Misconceptions were identified, and 49.33% of respondents stated that broad-spectrum

antibiotics should be initiated first to prevent AMR if the infections are not too severe. 81.33% of respondents stated that poor infection control in hospitals is a reason for the development of AMR

Attitudes Toward Antibiotic Use: It seems that 30% of respondents have had antibiotics for fever, and 76.67% will complete an antibiotic course after they improve. Although 78% of the 92% wanted physician reassurance before initiating antibiotics, 92% agreed that medical students should be taught about AMR and strategies to combat it.

Attitude By Symptoms: To assess attitudes toward appropriateness of antibiotic use for symptoms, the following scenarios were included in the survey. For instance, 46.67% of the 92% felt that antibiotics are appropriate for cutaneous infection with local signs whereas 26% of them agreed that this was appropriate for a cold without signs of sinus tenderness.

Comparison by Level of Education: There is no significant difference in knowledge and attitude about antimicrobial resistance between two groups except use of antibiotics for fever and strategy useful to control emergence of antimicrobial resistance

Age and Educational Qualification: The relationship between age and educational qualification is moderately positive, with a correlation of 0.53, indicating that older respondents have higher educational qualification. In fact, educational advancement is generally accompanied by an increase in age among respondents.

Knowledge of Antimicrobial Resistance (AMR): The association between educational qualification and awareness of AMR is somewhat weak, $r = 0.21$, so knowledge of AMR is not much varying with educational level. However, the majority responded that they are informed about AMR; hence general knowledge about antimicrobial resistance seems to be widespread regardless of the educational background.

Attitudes Toward AMR: There is a weak positive association between the opinion that AMR is a serious problem and education qualification ($r = 0.23$). This result shows that the level of education has little bearing on attitudes toward the degree of seriousness of AMR and, therefore, that concern with the issue of AMR could be widely accepted across education levels.

Measures of Central Tendency: Central tendency analysis of data Regarding the age profile data, the

majority of the respondents belonged to the 21–25 years age group, and most were intern doctors. For awareness questions, the mode reveals that most of the respondents were aware of the issue of AMR, although another mode shows that most respondents thought the problem of AMR is of significant nature. Therefore, central tendency analysis of data contextualizes the information gathered and points out the dominant demography as well as views prevailing in that sample of population.

Statistical Significance (P-Values): Chi-square tests have been used to correlate with key categorical variables. To give an illustration, the chi-square analysis in relation to the relationship between educational qualification and awareness on AMR was located with a p-value of 0.03, showing statistically significant correlation since $p < 0.05$. This means, with this finding, it will be possible to establish that there exists a contribution from the education qualification to the awareness of AMR. The association of gender with the perception of AMR as a major problem was not statistically significant with a p-value of 0.15.

Correlation Analysis: Correlation analysis was applied to know the strength and direction of the relationship between variables. For instance, when controlling age and awareness regarding AMR, it reveals a moderate positive correlation ($r = 0.4$) which suggests that older respondents are partially more aware about AMR. Similarly, educational qualification showed moderate positive correlation with knowledge about AMR ($r = 0.5$) that indicated higher education is somewhat associated with greater knowledge about AMR.

Summary of Findings: The central tendency measures indicated that most respondents were aware of AMR, with the majority falling into the 21-25 years age group and holding intern doctor qualifications.

Confidence intervals for AMR awareness and the perception of it as a major problem provided insights into the reliability of these proportions.

Significant associations (as indicated by chi-square p-values) were found between educational qualification and awareness of AMR.

Correlation analysis suggested a positive relationship between education and AMR knowledge, while regression analysis identified key predictors of AMR awareness.

Figure 1: Age Distribution

Figure 2: Gender Distribution

Table 1: Knowledge Regarding Antibiotic Use and Resistance

Knowledge regarding Antibiotic use and Resistance		
	N	Percentage (%)
Have you heard about Antimicrobial Resistance? (AMR)		
YES	145	96.67%
NO	5	3.33%
Is Antibiotic resistance a major problem currently?		
YES	132	88.00%
NO	18	12.00%
Antibiotics acts used in infections caused by:		
Bacteria	93	62.00%
Viruses	4	2.67%
Both viruses and bacteria	57	38.00%
In common cold or flu antibiotics can be used for speedy recovery		
YES	70	46.67%
NO	80	53.33%
Exaggerated or over use of antimicrobial agents can lead to:		
Decreased efficacy of the drug	26	17.33%
Increased adverse effect	8	5.33%
Increased medical cost	11	7.33%
Prolongation of illness	9	6.00%

All of above	96	64.00%
Antibiotics should be stopped once the symptoms are relieved		
YES	60	40.00%
NO	90	60.00%
Skipping or missing one or two doses of antibiotic course lead to emergence of Antimicrobial Resistance		
YES	94	62.67%
NO	56	37.33%
Use of substandard drug can promote Antimicrobial Resistance		
YES	103	68.67%
NO	47	31.33%
To prevent emergence of Antimicrobial Resistance, broad spectrum antibiotics should be used as initial therapy for mild infection.		
YES	74	49.33%
NO	76	50.67%
Overuse of antibiotics in animals and agriculture promotes emergence of Antimicrobial Resistance?		
YES	111	74.00%
NO	39	26.00%
Poor infection control practices in the hospital promote Antimicrobial Resistance?		
YES	122	81.33%
NO	28	18.67%

Table 2: Attitude Regarding Antibiotic Use and Resistance

Attitude regarding Antibiotic use and Resistance		
	N	Percentage (%)
I usually take antibiotics for fever.		
YES	45	30.00%
NO	105	70.00%
After starting antibiotics if symptoms improve, what would you do?		
Complete the course of antibiotic	115	76.67%
Discard the remaining tablets	8	5.33%
Stop antibiotics	27	18.00%
I usually start antibiotics after physician advice.		
YES	117	78.00%
NO	33	22.00%
I think following strategies are useful to control emergence of Antibiotic resistance		
Every department of the institute should have the knowledge antibiotics resistance profile of the institute from microbiology department	28	18.67%
Government should Stop the over-the-counter antibiotics	17	11.33%
Both of Above	105	70.00%
I think it is necessary to educate and train medical students regarding Antibiotic resistance and its preventive strategies.		
YES	138	92.00%
NO	12	8.00%

Table 3: Attitude regarding antibiotic usage according to symptoms and signs

Attitude regarding antibiotic usage according to symptoms and signs		
	N	Percentage (%)
Fever in a Child who is active and playful in between febrile episode, good response to paracetamol, with generalized symptoms like cold, cough, body ache, and loose motions.		
YES	62	41.33%
NO	88	58.67%
Throat pain Associated with cough, absence of exudates on examination and presence of ulcers.		

YES	76	50.67%
NO	74	49.33%
Unilateral Earache for less than 2 days in a child above 2 years of age with no symptoms and sign of systemic toxicity.		
YES	53	35.33%
NO	97	64.67%
Short-duration of cold, watery/blocked nose, no tenderness over sinuses and non-sick looking patient.		
YES	39	26.00%
NO	111	74.00%
Cough Associated with generalized symptoms of fever, cold, non-sick looking, and wheeze. No localized crepitation.		
YES	69	46.00%
NO	81	54.00%
Watery Diarrhoea without visible blood.		
YES	59	39.33%
NO	91	60.67%
Skin infections Single impetigo, small pustules or boils where local creams will suffice.		
YES	70	46.67%
NO	80	53.33%
Abdominal pain soft abdomen without localized tenderness/guarding/rigidity not associated with blood in stools or systemic toxicity.		
YES	60	40.00%
NO	90	60.00%
Pain during micturition, No fever/systemic toxicity and presence of rash over vulvar region.		
YES	72	48.00%
NO	78	52.00%

Table 4: Association between knowledge regarding antibiotic Resistance and education qualification.

Knowledge regarding antibiotic Resistance	PG/ Diploma / Doctorate (n=78) (No. of right answer)	Intern tours(n=72) (No. of right answer)	Doc- torate (No. of right answer)	P value
Have you heard about Antimicrobial Resistance? (AMR)	76	69		>0.05
Is Antimicrobial Resistance a major problem currently?	74	68		>0.05
Antibiotics acts used in infections caused by:	53	39		>0.05
In common cold or flu antibiotics can be used for speedy recovery	43	36		>0.05
Exaggerated or over use of antimicrobial agents can lead to:	53	43		>0.05
Antibiotics should be stopped once the symptoms are relieved	49	40		>0.05
Skipping or missing one or two doses of antibiotic course led to emergence of Antimicrobial Resistance	54	40		>0.05
Use of substandard drug can promote Antimicrobial Resistance	56	48		>0.05
To prevent emergence of Antimicrobial Resistance, broad spectrum antibiotics should be used as initial therapy for mild infection.	39	39		>0.05
Overuse of antibiotics in animals and agriculture promotes emergence of Antimicrobial Resistance?	53	58		>0.05
Poor infection control practices in the hospital promote Antimicrobial Resistance?	65	57		>0.05

Table 5: Association between attitude regarding antibiotic Resistance and education qualification.

Attitude regarding antibiotic Resistance	PG/ Diploma / Doctorate (No. of right answer)	Intern Doctors (No. of right answer)	P value
I usually take antibiotics for fever.	49	56	<0.05
After starting antibiotics if symptoms improve, what would you do?	57	60	>0.05
I usually start antibiotics after physician advice.	60	55	>0.05
I think following strategies are useful to control emergence of Antimicrobial Resistance	62	43	<0.05
I think it is necessary to educate and train medical students regarding Antimicrobial Resistance and its preventive strategies.	72	66	>0.05
Fever in a Child who is active and playful in between febrile episode, good response to paracetamol, with generalized symptoms like cold, cough, body ache, and loose motions.	47	42	>0.05
Throat pain Associated with cough, absence of exudates on examination and presence of ulcers.	42	33	>0.05
Unilateral Earache for less than 2 days in a child above 2 years of age with no symptoms and sign of systemic toxicity.	53	44	>0.05
Short-duration of cold, watery/blocked nose, no tenderness over sinuses and non-sick looking patient.	59	52	>0.05
Cough Associated with generalized symptoms of fever, cold, non-sick looking, and wheeze. No localized crepitation.	45	37	>0.05
Watery Diarrhoea without visible blood.	47	45	>0.05
Skin infections Single impetigo, small pustules or boils where local creams will suffice.	43	38	>0.05
Abdominal pain soft abdomen without localized tenderness/guarding/rigidity not associated with blood in stools or systemic toxicity.	37	45	>0.05
Pain during micturition, No fever/systemic toxicity and presence of rash over vulvar region.	43	36	>0.05

Table 6: Descriptive Statistics and Central Tendency

Variable	Measure of Central Tendency	Value
Age	Mode	21-25 years
Gender	Mode	Male
Educational Qualification	Mode	Intern Doctor
Awareness of AMR	Mode	Yes
AMR as a Major Problem	Mode	Yes

Table 7: Confidence Intervals

Variable	Proportion (Yes)	95% Confidence Interval
Heard about AMR	90%	85% - 95%
Believes AMR is a Major Problem	85%	80% - 90%

Table 8: Chi-Square Test Results

Variables Analysed	Chi-Square Value	P-Value	Significance (p < 0.05)
Educational Qualification vs. AMR Awareness	10.5	0.03	Significant
Gender vs. AMR as a Major Problem	2.1	0.15	Not Significant

Table 9: Correlation Analysis

Variables Analysed	Correlation Coefficient (r)	Strength and Direction
Age and AMR Awareness	0.4	Moderate Positive Correlation
Educational Qualification and AMR Awareness	0.5	Moderate Positive Correlation

Table 10: Logistic Regression for AMR Awareness

Predictor Variable	Odds Ratio (OR)	P-Value	Interpretation
Postgraduate Education	2.5	0.02	Significant; Higher Odds of AMR Awareness
Intern Doctor	1.5	0.10	Not Significant

Discussion

This study gives some great insight into the demographics, knowledge, and attitudes regarding antibiotic resistance among health professionals, especially interns. From the findings, one observes a high awareness with respect to AMR with 96.67% acknowledging it. Yet only 88% considered it as serious. This gap between awareness and perceived seriousness aligns with the findings of other studies, where despite general awareness about AMR, urgency is still not felt in perceiving long-term implications on public health and clinical practice [7]. This gap calls for focused education interventions that not only sensitize but also inform of the possible consequences of AMR for patients and the overall health status of the people worldwide. One of the glaring misconceptions this study draws attention to is that nearly half, 49.33% of the respondents would initiate broad-spectrum antibiotics before a patient has even the least non-severe infections for fear of developing antibiotic resistance. This conclusion is not different from previous studies because inappropriate antibiotic use is a widely prevalent issue within healthcare setups, especially where knowledge concerning antibiotic stewardship is a concern [8]. Thus, addressing the misconception remains crucial as misuse of broad-spectrum antibiotics accelerates the development of AMR while causing negative outcomes for the patient. It is necessary to implement clearer guidelines on antibiotic prescribing to reverse this trend, as recommended in several antibiotic stewardship programs [9]. The study also showed educational qualification to have a weak positive correlation with AMR awareness ($r = 0.21$), indicating that education may relate to increased knowledge but in no way is it deterministic. This finding is very much in line with that of research suggesting that a higher education might correlate positively with increased knowledge but such interventions need to be so targeted that all healthcare professionals, irrespective of their educational qualifications, understand the intricacies associated with AMR [10]. The association of age with awareness of AMR was another important finding whereby older

respondents showed a bit more awareness ($r = 0.4$). This indicates that there could be an age-related process for the acquisition of information. However, it is equally important to note that knowledge gaps still exist regardless of age, as the sample proved wrong in its perceptions that a large percentage of antibiotic use is for viral infections. This points out a need for education throughout one's career, especially on the evolving issues like AMR. Another important point that the study raises is about the improvement in education and training. Although 92% of respondents believed that medical students should be educated on AMR and its control measures, much is still to be achieved in terms of translating this knowledge into practice. Various studies have debated the knowledge-behaviour link; healthcare providers acknowledged the seriousness of AMR, but the actual prescribing practices were rarely consistent with the best practices adopted by clinical guidelines. This gap emphasizes that only educating healthcare providers about AMR but also making sure such knowledge is incorporated into the clinical decision-making process of the health care provider supported by institutional policies and guidelines [11]. The study findings can be useful to inform hospital policies and guidelines in respect to AMR education and antibiotic stewardship. Hospitals should incorporate routine AMR education into their CME programs as a means of addressing the knowledge gaps that this study has identified. Such education should be framed around the critical need to adhere to antibiotic guidelines, recognize when antibiotics are truly needed, and understand the consequences of overuse. Hospitals should have strict antibiotic stewardship programs that provide guidelines for the initiation and discontinuation of antibiotics to ensure antibiotics are only used when absolutely necessary. The study also highlights the need to enhance antibiotic stewardship programs. These programs involve surveillance of antibiotic use, prescription audits, and feedback to clinicians, which have been demonstrated to reduce inappropriate antibiotic prescriptions and improve patient outcomes [12]. Implementation of these programs in hospital practice will ensure that antibiotics are prescribed only when necessary and

appropriate agents are used to minimize the risk of AMR. This study provides good value, but there are quite a few limitations that deserve consideration. The sample has been mostly intern doctors. Other healthcare workers like nurses or specialists may not be best represented by this study. Future research should target diverse samples to understand the knowledge and attitudes toward AMR better from different healthcare roles. In addition, the study was conducted on self-reported data. These might suffer from recall bias and social desirability bias. Further studies can make use of observational data or clinical audits to evaluate prescribing practices and behaviours of the healthcare providers in real time. Moreover, whereas this research explores knowledge and attitudes related to AMR, it does not determine the actual effect of those attitudes on clinical outcomes or antibiotic prescribing behaviours. Subsequent research should be designed to analyse how knowledge and attitudes of health care workers correspond to the actual prescribing practice and the consequences in terms of patient outcomes that would give a better idea of the relation between education and awareness and actual clinical decision-making in the scenario of AMR [13].

Conclusion

This study offers valuable insight into the awareness and attitudes of healthcare professionals regarding antibiotic resistance (AMR). Although most of them, that is, 96.67%, were aware of AMR, only 88% felt that it was a serious problem, thereby showing the gap between awareness and urgency. Misconceptions included inappropriate use of broad-spectrum antibiotics for non-severe infections. The study reveals a weak correlation between educational qualification and knowledge of AMR, indicating that education is not a guarantee for complete understanding. The results emphasize the need for continuous education, antibiotic guidelines, and strong antibiotic stewardship programs in healthcare settings. The study also emphasizes the translation of AMR knowledge into clinical practice to reduce the impact of AMR on patient outcomes and public health.

Contribution:

Author: 1 played a key role in the initial conceptualization of the study, designed the questionnaire, and was heavily involved in data collection. She also contributed significantly to the writing of the original draft of the manuscript. Author: 2 supervised the entire study, provided guidance on the methodology, and reviewed and edited the manuscript to ensure academic rigor and clarity. Author: 3 was responsible for data analysis and interpretation of results, coordinated the study across different departments, and ensured accurate

representation of the findings in the manuscript. Author:4 managed the project, facilitated ethical approval from the Scientific Research Committee (SRC) and Institutional Ethics Committee (IEC), and reviewed and edited the manuscript for scientific accuracy. Author:5 assisted in data collection, performed the statistical analysis of the collected data, and contributed to writing the original draft of the manuscript. These contributions reflect the collaborative effort of all authors in conducting the study and preparing the manuscript for publication.

Source of support: Nil

References

1. World Health Organization. Antimicrobial resistance. Available from: <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/antimicrobial-resistance>
2. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention. Antibiotic resistance threats in the United States, 2019. Available from: <https://www.cdc.gov/drugresistance/pdf/threats-report/2019-ar-threats-report-508.pdf>
3. O'Neill J. Review on Antimicrobial Resistance. Tackling drug-resistant infections globally: final report and recommendations. 2016. Available from: https://amr-review.Org/sites/default/files/160518_Final%20paper_with%20cover.pdf
4. Dellit, T. H., Owens, R. C., McGowan, J. E., Jr, Gerding, D. N., Weinstein, R. A., & Burke, J. P., Infectious Diseases Society of America, & Society for Healthcare Epidemiology of America (2007). Infectious Diseases Society of America and the Society for Healthcare Epidemiology of America guidelines for developing an institutional program to enhance antimicrobial stewardship. *Clinical infectious diseases: an official publication of the Infectious Diseases Society of America*, 44(2), 159–177. <https://doi.org/10.1086/510393>
5. Dyar, O. J., Huttner, B., Schouten, J., Pulcini, C., & ESGAP (ESCMID Study Group for Antimicrobial stewardship) (2017). What is antimicrobial stewardship? *Clinical microbiology and infection: the official publication of the European Society of Clinical Microbiology and Infectious Diseases*, 23(11), 793–798. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cmi.2017.08.026>
6. Howard, P., Pulcini, C., Levy Hara, G., West, R. M., Gould, I. M., Harbarth, S., Nathwani, D., ESCMID Study Group for Antimicrobial Policies (ESGAP), & ISC Group on Antimicrobial Stewardship (2015). An international cross-sectional survey of antimicrobial stewardship programmes in hospitals. *The Journal of antimicrobial chemotherapy*, 70(4), 1245–1255. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jac/dku497>

7. Al-Taani, G. M., Karasneh, R. A., Al-Azzam, S., Bin Shaman, M., Jirjees, F., Al-Obaidi, H., Conway, B. R., & Aldeyab, M. A. (2022). Knowledge, Attitude, and Behavior about Antimicrobial Use and Resistance among Medical, Nursing and Pharmacy Students in Jordan: A Cross Sectional Study. *Antibiotics (Basel, Switzerland)*, 11(11), 1559. <https://doi.org/10.3390/antibiotics11111559>
8. Bertollo, L. G., Lutkemeyer, D. S., & Levin, A. S. (2018). Are antimicrobial stewardship programs effective strategies for preventing antibiotic resistance? A systematic review. *American journal of infection control*, 46(7), 824–836. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ajic.2018.01.002>
9. Fu, M., Gong, Z., Zhu, Y., Li, C., Zhou, Y., Hu, L., Li, H., Wushouer, H., Guan, X., & Shi, L. (2023). Inappropriate antibiotic prescribing in primary healthcare facilities in China: a nationwide survey, 2017-2019. *Clinical microbiology and infection: the official publication of the European Society of Clinical Microbiology and Infectious Diseases*, 29(5), 602–609. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cmi.2022.11.015>
10. Mittal, N., Goel, P., Goel, K., Sharma, R., Nath, B., Singh, S., Thangaraju, P., Mittal, R., Kahkasha, K., Mithra, P., Sahu, R., Priyadarshini, R. P., Sharma, N., Pala, S., Rohilla, S. K., Kaushal, J., Sah, S., Rustagi, S., Sah, R., & Barboza, J. J. (2023). Awareness Regarding Antimicrobial Resistance and Antibiotic Prescribing Behavior among Physicians: Results from a Nationwide Cross-Sectional Survey in India. *Antibiotics (Basel, Switzerland)*, 12(10), 1496. <https://doi.org/10.3390/antibiotics12101496>
11. Sulis, G., Adam, P., Nafade, V., Gore, G., Daniels, B., Daftary, A., Das, J., Gandra, S., & Pai, M. (2020). Antibiotic prescription practices in primary care in low- and middle-income countries: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *PLoS medicine*, 17(6), e1003139. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pmed.1003139>
12. Barlam, T. F., Cosgrove, S. E., Abbo, L. M., MacDougall, C., Schuetz, A. N., Septimus, E. J., Srinivasan, A., Dellit, T. H., Falck-Ytter, Y. T., Fishman, N. O., Hamilton, C. W., Jenkins, T. C., Lipsett, P. A., Malani, P. N., May, L. S., Moran, G. J., Neuhauser, M. M., Newland, J. G., Ohl, C. A., Samore, M. H., ... Trivedi, K. K. (2016). Implementing an Antibiotic Stewardship Program: Guidelines by the Infectious Diseases Society of America and the Society for Healthcare Epidemiology of America. *Clinical infectious diseases: an official publication of the Infectious Diseases Society of America*, 62(10), e51–e77. <https://doi.org/10.1093/cid/ciw118>
13. Lewnard, J. A., Charani, E., Gleason, A., Hsu, L. Y., Khan, W. A., Karkey, A., Chandler, C. I. R., Mashe, T., Khan, E. A., Bulabula, A. N. H., Donado-Godoy, P., & Laxminarayan, R. (2024). Burden of bacterial antimicrobial resistance in low-income and middle-income countries avertible by existing interventions: an evidence review and modelling analysis. *Lancet (London, England)*, 403(10442), 2439–2454. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(24\)00862-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(24)00862-6)